

TOXIGENIC POTENTIAL OF *Alternaria porri* ON ONION (*Allium cepa* L.)

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ABSTRACT

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is the important vegetable crop. Under favourable condition onion is attacked by various diseases. Among these diseases, purple blotch caused by *Alternaria porri* is one of the predominant disease of onion. Toxigenic potential of *Alternaria porri* was assessed against seed germination, seedling growth of onion and antibacterial activity against some phytopathogenic bacteria. Diseased samples were collected from the Department of Horticulture, Chilli and Vegetable Research Unit, Dr. P.D.K.V., Akola and farmers field at village Shivapur, Taluka-Barshitakali, District-Akola during the year 2015, resortal for isolation and *Alternaria porri* was observed as a predominant fungus in the diseased samples collected from different locations. Isolation frequency of *Alternaria porri* was observed in the range of 45 to 60 per cent. The seed germination, seedling growth of onion were adversely affected due to the culture filtrates of *Alternaria porri*. The metabolites produced by *Alternaria porri* inhibited the growth of *Bacillus subtilis* and was found ineffective against *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Xanthomonas axonopodis* pv. *Citri* and *Erwinia caratovora*.

(Key words: *Alternaria porri*, purple blotch, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*)

INTRODUCTION

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is an important bulb crop of India belonging to family Alliaceae. It is one of the most important winter vegetable crop of India. It is a nutritious vegetable and contains a good amount of Vitamin A and C, rich source of minerals (calcium, magnese and iron) and dietary fibres. It is cool season crop which thrives best in relative cool and moist climate. Purple blotch disease, which is caused by *Alternaria porri* (Ellis) Cif., is one of the most destructive disease restricted to the genus *Allium* and widespread in many regions of the world (Cramer,2000). Purple blotch disease of onion cause significant reduction in foliar production (Utikar and Padule,1980) and bulb yield (Gupta and Pathak, 1988). The disease is more severe on seed crop as compared to bulb crop sometimes causing a 100% loss of onion seed production. (Singh *et al.*,1992). Among these, purple blotch caused by '*Alternaria porri*' is one of the major disease of onion. The name purple blotch for this disease was proposed by Nolla (1927). He named the causal organism as *Alternaria allil* which was later amended to *Alternaria porri*. Ajrekar (1920) made first report on leaf spot and blight disease on onion in Bombay and attributed it to *Alternaria* spp. The losses about 50-100% due to purple blotch of onion have been reported by Shahanaz *et al.* (2007). The pathogen *Alternaria porri* destructs the leaf tissue which hinder the stimulus for bulb initiation and delay in bulbing and maturation. Sever attack

on flowering, onion can completely girdle flower stalks with necrotic tissue, causing their collapse and total loss of seed production capacity (Agale *et al.*, 2014). Germination as well as seedling growth (radical and plumule elongation) were adversely effected up to 80% when the seed were treated with fungal culture filtrate (Madhavi *et al.*, 2012). The influence of environment on incidence of disease was studied by some workers from different part of countries and reported that high rainfall and high humidity favoured the disease development. *Alternaria porri* on onion occurred following a long period relative humidity > 90% or dew deposition and temperature ranges between 20-25°C (Gupta and Pathak, 1986; Everts and Lacy, 1996).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of diseased samples

Onion leaves infected with *Alternaria* purple blotch were collected from the Department of Horticulture, Chilli and Vegetable Research Unit, Dr. P.D.K.V., Akola and farmers field at village Shivapur, Taluka-Barshitakali, District-Akola during the year 2015. Based on symptoms, microscopic examination of diseased samples association of the pathogen as *Alternaria porri* was recorded.

Glassware, plasticware and other materials

Petri plates, glass petri dishes, conical flasks, test tubes, blotter paper and roll paper towel were used in the present studies.

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Preparation of potato dextrose agar

Potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium was used for isolation and maintenance of cultures.

The medium was prepared with following ingredients

Peeled potatoes	-	200 gm
Dextrose	-	20 gm
Agar agar	-	20 gm
Distilled water	-	1000 ml

Disinfection / sterilization of laboratory materials

To detect the fungi on leaves, the plates were washed with cleaning powder under running water, dried and then disinfected with denatured spirit. However, glass plates were sterilized in hot air oven at 180°C for 1 hr. before use.

Isolation of pathogen by tissue isolation method

Infected leaf samples were cut into small pieces with sterilized blade and disinfected with sodium hypochloride (0.2%) solution for two minutes. Pieces were washed with three changes of sterilized distilled water and bits after dried on sterilized filter paper and around flame of spirit lamp were placed on solidified PDA medium in plate. Each plate contained five bits. The plates were incubated at room temperature (28±2°C). All these operations were carried out aseptically. The plates were examined regularly. Colonies were developed around the each bit were examined and sub cultured. Based on morphological characters and published literature the fungus was identified as *Alternaria porri*. The pure culture was transferred on PDA slants and maintained for further studies.

Purification and maintenance of fungal culture

Culture was purified by following hyphal tip method (Vincent, 1947) and culture obtained was maintained on potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium slants at room temperature by adopting subsequent sub culturing at periodical, regular intervals. Seven days old culture was used for further studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Association of *Alternaria porri* and other fungi recorded in collected diseased samples

Sr.No.	Locations	No. of bits used for isolation	No. of bits yielded fungi	Fungi obtained (No. of bits)		Occurrence of fungi (%)		Name of other Fungi
				<i>Alternaria porri</i>	other fungi	<i>Alternaria porri</i>	Other fungi	
1.	Shivapur Department of Horticulture, Dr. P. D. K.V., Akola	30	24	18	6	60	24	<i>Fusarium</i> spp.
2.	Chilli and Vegetable Research Unit, Dr. P. D. K.V., Akola	25	20	10	7	40	28	<i>Rhizoctonia bataticola</i> <i>Curuvularia lunata</i>
3.		20	15	9	6	45	30	

Pathogenicity test by spray inoculation method

Pathogenicity of fungus was proved by Inoculation of seventeen days old onion seedlings. The fungal suspension was prepared (4× 10⁴ spores ml⁻¹ of water) from seven days old culture and used for inoculation. The seedlings were inoculated by automizing them with fungal suspension. The inoculated and un inoculated seedlings were covered with polyethylene bag for 48 hrs to provide humidity and favourable condition for disease development. Irrigated the seedlings daily to maintain moisture and watched for appearance of disease symptoms on leaves. Chlorotic oval eye shaped lesions were observed after three days of inoculation and full grown purple oval shaped lesion observed after ten days of inoculation. Further the lesion coalesced and spread rapidly on leaf blade and affected leaves showed drying from tip downward after twenty one days of inoculation. Re-isolation were made from infected part of inoculated leaves, yielded the same pathogen, whereas control plants remained healthy.

Preparation of culture filtrates of *Alternaria porri*

To study the phytotoxic effect of fungal culture filtrates on seed germination and seedling growth of onion, the fungus was cultured on Czapek-dox broth for 30 days. At the day of incubation, the fungal culture filtrates were collected under aseptic conditions and tested for phytotoxicity against seed germination and seedling growth of onion. To assess the effect of culture filtrates of *Alternaria porri* on seed germination and seedlings growth of onion, roll towel method was used.

Preparation of fungal metabolites produced by *Alternaria porri*

Alternaria porri was cultured on yeast extract sucrose medium (YES) for 30 days at room temperature as stationary culture. At the day of incubation, the fungal culture mat was separated by filtration through Whatman No.1 filter paper and the filtrates were collected. The culture filtrates was extracted with diethyl ether. The extract was evaporated to dryness on water bath avoiding excess heat. The residues were dissolved in 1.0 ml of diethyl ether, transferred to glass vial and preserved for testing of antibacterial activity against some selected phytopathogenic bacteria.

Fig.1. Association of *Alternaria porri* and other fungi in diseased samples

The data regarding frequencies of isolation are given in Table 1. It is seen that the majority of bits yielded the fungus *Alternaria porri* in the range of 40-60 per cent. Hence, *Alternaria porri* was observed to be predominant fungus in collected diseased samples. However, the association frequency of other fungi was recorded between the range of 24-30%. Wadile (2011) and Umbarakar (2013) have reported the association frequency of *Alternaria carthami* and *Alternaria brassicicola* in the range of 40-64% and 33-40% in the sunflower and cauliflower respectively.

Pathogenicity test

The diseased symptoms were noticed within 7 to 21 days on the tip of the older leaves as small, whitish, sunken, oval shaped lesion which later on became elliptical or oblong, which brown to purple at the centre and surrounded by a light brown area. Further the lesions coalesce and spread rapidly on leaf blade and affected leaves

showed complete drying from tip downward within 21 day. These leaves were collected and used for re-isolation yielded same pathogen, identity, confirmed and it is evident that the *Alternaria porri* was found pathogenic. Agale *et al.* (2012), Pandotra (1964) and Sekar *et al.* (2017) established the pathogenicity of *Alternaria porri* by following Koch's postulate.

Symptoms of *Alternaria porri* in naturally infected field

Brown lesions with reddish-purple margins were noticed. The purple blotch symptoms development starts from the older leaves as small, whitish, sunken, oval shaped lesion which later on became elliptical or oblong, brown to purple at the centre and surrounded by a light brown area. Further the lesion coalesce and spread rapidly on leaf blade and effected leaves showed drying from tip downward. Madhavi *et al.* (2012) and Agale *et al.* (2014) observed the similar symptoms of purple blotch of onion on various parts of the plants viz., leaves, stem, seeds, flower, bulb etc.

Plate 1. Pathogenicity test

Plate 2. Symptoms of leaf blight and purple blotch of onion caused by *Alternaria porri*

Phytotoxicity of culture filtrates of *Alternaria porri* on seed germination and seedlings growth of onion

To study the phytotoxic effect of culture filtrate on seed germination and seedling growth of onion the presoaked seeds in fungal culture filtrates were placed on moistened roll towel paper. Germination and seedling growth were adversely affected by 78% and 42.84% with reduction in seedling vigour index (44.77) when the seeds were treated with culture filtrates of *Alternaria porri*. Results on the same line have been reported by Madhavi *et al.* (2012). They reported that the germination as well as seedling growth were adversely affected upto 80% when the seeds were treated with culture filtrates of *Alternaria porri*. The inhibition or root length of

onion seedling (80%) and chlorotic spot (5.00 mm) on onion leaves after three days due to sixteen days old culture filtrates of *Alternaria porri* with pH 8 was also shown by Khare and Goswami (1996). Suemitsu *et al.* (1995) observed that porriitoxin produce by *Alternaria porri* had an inhibitory effects on the seedling growth of stone leek and lettuce. The phytotoxic compounds consist of metabolites phytoxin sulfonic acid with an isoindoline skeleton. Shirurkar *et al.* (2014) reported the same results, who reported that culture filtrates of *Aspergillus niger* adversely affected the seed germination of local and African tall by 75% and Amber by 60% with the reduction in vigour index 372, 720 and 1408 in the varieties of maize respectively.

Table 2. Effect of culture filtrates of *Alternaria porri* on seed germination and seedlings growth of onion

Sr. No.	Seed germination (%)	Seedling length (cm)	Seedling Vigour Index
1. Treated	22.00	2.03	44.77
2. Untreated	88.00	4.75	380

Effect of fungal metabolites of *Alternaria porri* on bacterial pathogens

The metabolites produced by *Alternaria porri* were screened for antibacterial potential against some phytopathogenic bacteria using seeded plate technique. The metabolites adversely affected the growth (17.4 mm) of *Bacillus subtilis*. However, the metabolites were found ineffective against *Pseudomonas fluorescens*, *Xanthomonas*

axonopodis pv. *citri* and *Erwinia caratovora*. The present results are similar with the findings of Madhavi *et al.* (2012). They reported the metabolites produced by *Alternaria porri* adversely affected the growth of *Bacillus subtilis* (240 mm²), *Escherichia coli* (235 mm²) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (120 mm²) but ineffective against *Pseudomonas fluorescens* and *Xanthomonas axonopodis* pv. *citri*.

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of metabolites produced by *Alternaria porri* against some phytopathogenic bacteria

Bacteria	Zone of inhibition (mm)
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	17.4
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	00
<i>Xanthomonas axonopodis</i> pv. <i>citri</i>	00
<i>Erwinia caratovora</i>	00